

Relationship between Stress and Coping Strategies among Hosteled Students

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Vol. 1, No. 1 (2023)

Pages: 01 – 07

Key Words

Stress, Coping Strategies, Hosteled Students

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Abstract: *The current study aims to analyze the relationship between stress and coping strategies among hosteled students of Abdul Wail Khan University Mardan, Pakistan. Hostel is for those who stay in other area for their education, job purpose. Hosteled students experience higher level of stress than students who lived off-campus. Some of them have found higher level of stress than those who stayed in home. Hosteled students use coping strategies to cope with their stress. Coping strategies refers to an action. The researchers investigate the relationship of stress and coping strategies. For this purpose the researchers collected 200 data from hosteled students 100 from male 100 from female at Abdul Wail Khan University Mardan (AWKUM) made up our sample. This study discovered that stress and coping strategies there is a negative and low association between dependent and independent variable. The results additionally indicate that within the regression analysis, which sequentially explicates the variations stage by stage, there exists an inverse relationship between stress and stress coping strategies. Furthermore, statistical scrutiny reveals a statistically significant but low negative correlation between stress coping strategies and stress at a predetermined level of significance.*

Introduction

Previous research indicates that hostels are for people who need to continue in academic learning away from home because they experience numerous challenges that might produce many stressful occurrences in their lives. Some people acclimatize quickly to harsh circumstances, while others take longer to adjust to hostel life. The attractions and pleasures of hostel living are numerous. Students from outlying areas live in a hostel to finish their studies. The hostel employees cooked the majority of the food served to hostel students. Stress is a natural and healthy reaction to life's difficulties; nevertheless, when it becomes overpowering, it may have a severe influence on both psychological and physical health. It is critical to recognize the signs of stress and take appropriate action to control it. Stress develops when a person feels that he or she is unable to satisfy expectations and mobilizes all available resources to do so (Selye, 1956). The notion of change, as defined by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), corresponds to the concept of issue focused coping, which is directed towards coping with stresses. Change coping strategy, according to Rabenu and Yaniv (2017), may be characterized as an active process of fixing the problem caused by stress, even in the face of hurdles.

Students who are not living in their homes and are staying outside the house and that area is related to some institution called hostel and the students living in their termed hosteleries as far as

certain students the hostel life is full of joy and charm. Students residing in a hostel come from many cases, faiths, socioeconomic backgrounds, and geographical locations. When they enrolled at the hostel at first, all of the pupils are absolutely unfamiliar with one another, however, as soon as they form a friendship tie among themselves. The dorm affiliated to an institute no longer distinguishes between affluent and poor students. Hostel life is defined as living in a shared residence with other people, generally students, travellers, or working professionals. The major advantages of living in a hostel are financial savings over living in a private flat, the ability to meet and socialize with individuals from all backgrounds, and the convenience of having basic services supplied. Residents in hostels are more determined, self-sufficient, and confident, and they have a more positive attitude than non-resident students (Rafique, Mahmood, Warraich & Rehman, 2021).

However, there are drawbacks to hostel life, such as restricted privacy, common living areas that are not always kept clean, and having to cope with a noisy or inconsiderate flat mate. Students must solve difficulties on their own in hostels, which feature separate males and female dormitories (Tariq, Tariq, Tariq & Jawed, 2020). Those seeking hostel living should carefully assess the trade-offs and select a hostel that matches their requirements and preferences. Hostels can range from simple, low-cost accommodations to more luxury ones with private rooms and shared toilets. All of these issues may result in aberrant behavior or produce further psychological issues (Kumar & Bhukar, 2013).

Overall, hostel living may be a memorable and enjoyable experience for individuals who like meeting new people and are willing to sacrifice some privacy for financial savings and social possibilities. As hostel students live away from home, they acquire a sense of independence. Students who have previously lived in a hostel would readily adjust in a hostile atmosphere, unlike students who are new to hostel life. Hostel life introduces social contact amongst students because they can share rooms, washrooms, dining rooms, TV rooms, cafés, and so on. As they were trained for various purposes in their lives, the pupils learned about collaboration. Students who reside in a hostel do a lot of things on their own since they encounter a lot of challenges or issues such as a lack of sufficient food, bad management, and so on (Rafique, Mahmood, Warraich & Rehman, 2021).

Stress is typical among students, but hostelizeed students experience a distinct degree of stress. Stress is an uncomfortable scenario that occurs to an individual whenever they are in a difficult position (Shabbir et al., 2021). People are affected differently by stressors based on their environment and how they comprehend the event. They can induce physical symptoms like headaches, exhaustion, and sleeplessness, as well as psychological responses like anxiety, despair, and anger. When a person is subjected to a stressful event, the body produces a psychological response known as the "fight or flight" response. This is an unconscious natural reaction to danger that involves the production of hormones like adrenaline and cortisol. These hormones produce mental and physical transformations such as higher heart rate, quicker breathing, and enhanced sensitivity. The body's response to a stressful event is not always consistent. A variety of factors including their emotional resilience as well as their coping skills, some people may be able to manage with the stressor more successfully than others; for example, some people may be able to deal with a job loss more efficiently than others, while others may respond more strongly to a breakup. A stressor's influence might endure for a long time and can even develop to prolonged stress, which can have major health repercussions. It is critical for people to be aware of stressors and to practice appropriate stress management measures. This can involve relaxing strategies like deep breathing, exercise, and yoga, and also seeking expert treatment (Isaacs, 2008)

Lazarus and Folkman (1984) define stress management as the ongoing cognitive and behavioral endeavors aimed at addressing external and internal demands perceived as overwhelming or surpassing an individual's resources. This involves utilizing thoughts and actions to improve one's circumstances and alleviate stress levels. Coping strategies, as outlined by Sreeramareddy et al., (2007), encompass a range of specific behavioral and psychological efforts employed by individuals to confront, adapt to, or mitigate stressful events, with these strategies often being influenced by individual personality traits. Individuals who effectively manage stress typically exhibit positive self-perceptions, optimism, and resilience in adverse situations, along with

the ability to select appropriate coping mechanisms for encountered stressors. Conversely, those who struggle with stress often exhibit contrasting personality traits, such as low self-esteem and a pessimistic outlook on life. Nazeer & Sultana, (2014) similarly define coping strategies as the dynamic cognitive and behavioral actions utilized by individuals to manage, diminish, or regulate stressors. In essence, coping strategies entail actions or methods employed to address or modify one's response to stressful or unpleasant situations.

It's important to understand that coping strategies are consciously planned efforts to overcome a personal or interpersonal problem in a way that will help in minimizing, overcoming, or tolerating stress or conflict. In order to cope with stress, our bodies and minds need ways of calming them down afterwards. In terms of coping strategies, there are actually two main categories of them: emotion-focused coping and solution-focused coping. Skinner et al. (2003) found that these differed in terms of the number and range of coping categories they offered. The coping strategies were divided into three categories. This approach emphasizes the importance of individuals' subjective evaluations of their ability to cope with stressors, highlighting the dynamic interplay between cognitive appraisal and adaptive responses to stressful situations.

Methodology

Undergraduate students from several disciplines of Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan were selected. The ages of the participants varied from 18 to 25 years old. Each semester's participants were chosen. We utilised standardised questionnaires with two variables to obtain data. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: demographic information and items linked to the variables on a 5-point Likert scale which ranged from strongly agree to Strongly Disagree. To pick participants who would be representative of all university students, we used a Non-Probability Convenience sampling approach.

Carver's 1997 stress coping strategies measure, which had 28 questions on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to strongly disagree, was employed. The stress coping strategies scale has an internal reliability of 0.811. Data was collected using questionnaires that were divided into three sections: demographic information, the Stress Coping Strategies Scale, and the Perceived Stress Scale. The ethical norms specified in the 2002 APA code addressing confidentiality, voluntary participation, the opportunity to withdraw, and the safeguarding of dignity were scrupulously followed. Participants were told of the study's aim and thanked for their participation. The questions took about 10 to 15 minutes to complete.

Result

Frequency table

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	96	48.0	48.0	48.0
	female	104	52.0	52.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Out of 200 respondents 96 were found male with a valid percent of 48% and 104 were found female with a valid percent of 52%.

Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	upper	22	11.0	11.0	11.0
	middle	104	52.0	52.0	63.0
	lower	74	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

According to socio economics status out 200 respondents 22 were found from upper class with a percent of 11.0. 104 were found from middle class with a percent of 52.0 and similarly 74 were found from lower class family with a percent of 37.0.

Area		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	urban	104	52.0	52.0	52.0
	rural	96	48.0	48.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

According to Area out of 200 respondent 104 were found from urban area with a 52.0% percent similarly 96 respondents were found from rural area with a 48.0%.

Correlation Results:

Correlation analysis serves as a pertinent method to elucidate the relationship between two variables under study. It is particularly suitable for examining the association between stress coping strategies and stress levels. This analytical approach allows researchers to assess the degree of dependence or interdependence between these variables, thereby providing insights into how individuals' coping mechanisms may be influenced by their perceived levels of stress.

Tableno4

Correlations

		stress	Stress coping strategy
QD	Pearson Correlation	1	-.172
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	200	200
QID	Pearson Correlation	-.172	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	200	200

Data from table 4 shows the relationship among stress coping strategy and stress. Such analyses provide that the link between stress coping strategy and stress is -.172. A correlation coefficient of -.172 indicates a reasonable strength of relationship between the variables under consideration. The Pearson correlation significance (2-tailed) for stress coping strategy is 0.015, which is below the conventional level of significance (0.05), suggesting a statistically significant association between the variables. This negative correlation implies that there is a low and negative relationship between the dependent and independent variables. In other words, the independent variable is negatively related to the dependent variable, indicating that as one variable increases, the other tends to decrease.

Regression Results

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.172	.029	.025	4.44240

Table 1 displays a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.172, indicating a discernible association between the variables under investigation. The coefficient of determination (R-square) is reported as 0.029, which elucidates the proportion of variance in the stress coping strategy that is accounted for by changes in stress levels. Specifically, the mean value of R-square suggests that approximately 2.9% of the variability in stress coping strategy can be explained by variations in stress levels.

Table 2:ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	118.486	1	118.486	6.004	.015
Residual	3907.509	198	19.735		
Total	4025.995	199			

Table 2 presents an F-value of 6.004. The significance value associated with this model is reported as 0.15, which is less than the conventional threshold of 0.05. This indicates that the overall model is highly significant, suggesting that the variables included in the model collectively have a meaningful impact on the outcome.

Table 3 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
(Constant)	28.621	2.115		13.529	.000
Stress coping strategy	-.070	.029	-.172	-2.450	.015

Table 3 illustrates the standard coefficient, denoted by the negative sign (-) of -.172, indicating a negative association between stress and stress coping strategy. The statistical examination reveals a low negative link between stress coping strategy and stress at a specified level of significance. Additionally, the table provides estimations, with the coefficient of the constant being 28.621 and the coefficient of stress coping strategies being -.070. The negative sign associated with the coefficient of stress coping strategies signifies a negative impact of stress coping strategy on stress, suggesting that as stress coping strategies increase, stress levels tend to decrease. Constant t-ratio is 13.5, whereas stress coping strategy t-statistics -2.4. We may conclude that stress coping strategy has a negative influence on stress.

Discussion

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the connection between stress coping styles and stress levels among the participants. The correlation analysis highlights a negative relationship between stress coping strategies and stress, as evidenced by a Pearson correlation coefficient of -.172. This suggests a reasonable strength of relationship between the two variables. Additionally, the significance level of the correlation (2-tailed) is 0.015, which is lower than the standard threshold of 0.05, further reinforcing the negative association between stress coping strategies and stress. Further examination of the relationships between variables in Table 1 shows a link coefficient (r) of 0.172 and a coefficient of determination of 0.029, indicating that 2.9% of the variance in stress coping strategy can be attributed to variability in stress levels. The F-value of 6.004 in Table 2 is statistically significant at a level of 0.15, less than the standard 0.05 threshold, indicating that the overall model is highly significant. The standard coefficient in Table 3 reveals a negative association between stress and stress coping strategy, with the coefficient of stress coping strategy being -.070. This negative impact of stress coping strategy on stress is further supported by the negative t-statistic of -2.4, indicating a significant influence of stress coping strategies on stress levels. These findings are consistent with prior research efforts, as evidenced by studies conducted by Kumar & Bhukar, (2013), which have also underscored the influence of stress coping strategies on stress levels. The negative correlation uncovered in this study lends support to the notion that individuals employing particular coping mechanisms may experience diminished stress levels across various socio-economic and geographical settings. Collectively, these results enrich the existing understanding of stress management and offer valuable insights for both practitioners and researchers. Subsequent investigations could delve deeper into identifying the specific stress coping strategies that prove most efficacious in diverse social and economic environments, thereby building upon the groundwork established by this study. Building upon the insights gained from this study, it is recommended that practitioners and policymakers focus on promoting effective stress coping strategies, especially in lower socio-economic class and rural areas, where higher levels of stress were observed. Interventions aimed at enhancing coping skills and resilience could potentially mitigate the negative impact of stress in these specific demographics. Furthermore, future research endeavors could delve deeper into identifying and evaluating specific stress coping mechanisms that have shown to be particularly effective in diverse socio-economic and geographic settings. This could aid in the development of targeted interventions and programs tailored to the unique needs of different communities. The findings of this study not only contribute to the understanding of the

relationship between stress coping strategies and stress levels but also underscore the importance of addressing stress management from a holistic perspective that considers individual, socio-economic, and geographic factors. By implementing evidence-based interventions and continuing to expand the collective knowledge base, strides can be made towards improving overall wellbeing and resilience in diverse populations.

Conclusion

The prevalent tendency among students to overlook existing issues signals potentially serious mental and psychosocial challenges. It is plausible that female students may exhibit greater resilience to stress or encounter lower levels of pressure compared to their male counterparts. Therefore, undergraduate students at Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan are advised to augment positive stress (eustress) while mitigating negative stress (distress). Eustress can enhance students' performance and achievements, whereas distress may diminish their efficiency and accomplishments. It is anticipated that females may outnumber males. Correlation analysis suggests a reasonably strong relationship between variables, with a negative and modest association between the dependent and independent variables observed. Additionally, the overall model derived from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) demonstrates high significance. In conclusion, stress coping strategies appear to exert a negative impact on stress levels. This underscores the importance of adopting effective coping mechanisms to manage stress among students.

References

- Attiya, M., A. Al-Kamil, E., & Sharif, S. (2007). Stress and coping strategies among medical students in basrah. *The Medical Journal of Basrah University*, 25(2), 27–32. <https://doi.org/10.33762/mjbu.2007.48262>
- Chandra, P. (2018). A Study of Stress among Hostellers. *Home Sickness*, 8(2).
- Isaacs, A. S. A. (2008). Stress, coping strategies and social support amongst grade 11 students in historically disadvantaged schools (Doctoral dissertation, University of the Western Cape).
- Jahan, A., & Fatima, A. (2020). A Survey on Assessment of Stress Level among Hostellers (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 3715334). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3715334>
- Kumar, S., & Bhukar, J. P. (2013). Stress level and coping strategies of college students. *Journal of Physical Education and Sports Management*, 4(1), 5-11.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer publishing company.
- Mills, C. W. (1959). *The sociological imagination*. London, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.
- Nazeer, M., & Sultana, R. (2014). Stress and it's coping strategies in medical students. *Sch J App Med Sci*, 2(6D), 3111-117.
- Omonijo, D., Nnedum, O., Anyaegbunam, M., & Oludayo, O. (2015). Effects of roommate relationships on student's development. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 23(9), 2089-2098. doi: 10.5829/idosi.mejsr.2015.23.09.22428
- Rabenu, E., & Yaniv, E. (2017). Psychological resources and strategies to cope with stress at work. *International Journal of Psychological Research*, 10(2), 8-15.
- Rafique, G. M., Mahmood, K., Warraich, N. F., & Rehman, S. U. (2021). Readiness for Online Learning during COVID-19 pandemic: A survey of Pakistani LIS students. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(3), 102346.
- Rafique, S., & M, W. (2021). The Impact of Hostel Life on Personality Attributes of Young Adults: Case Study of a Public Sector University. *Psychology and Psychotherapy: Research Study*, 4(4), 1–4.
- Shabbir, T., Aslam, M., Kamran, H., Liaqat, M., Khan, R., & Saleem, M. (2021). Health Concerning Lifestyle and Risky Behaviours in University Going Female Students Residing In The Hostels of Lahore: Lifestyle and Risky Behaviours in Female Hostel Students. *DIET FACTOR (Journal of Nutritional & Food Sciences)*, 09–14. <https://doi.org/10.54393/df.v2i01.30>
- Shakeel, A., & Fatima, S. (2015). Life satisfaction and quality of life among hotelized and day scholar female students. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4(8), 119 – 127.

- Shireen Jawed, Benash Altaf, Rana Muhammad Tahir Salam, & Farhat Ijaz. (2020). Frequency of emotional disturbances among hostelites and day scholars medical students. *Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.47391/JPMA.562>
- Skinner, E. A., Edge, K., Altman, J., & Sherwood, H. (2003). Searching for the structure of coping: a review and critique of category systems for classifying ways of coping. *Psychological bulletin*, 129(2), 216.
- Sreeramareddy, C. T., Shankar, P. R., Binu, V., Mukhopadhyay, C., Ray, B., & Menezes, R. G. (2007). Psychological morbidity, sources of stress and coping strategies among undergraduate medical students of Nepal. *BMC Medical Education*, 7(1), 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-7-26>.
- Tariq, S., Tariq, S., Tariq, S., & Jawed, S. (2020). Perceived stress, severity and sources of stress among female medical students in a private medical college in Pakistan. *JPMA*, 2019, 162-167.